

INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF PHARMACEUTICAL RESEARCH

SYNTHESIS AND ANTIMICROBIAL ACTIVITY OF 1-(4-CHLOROPHENYL)-2-(3-SULPHOXYPHENYL)-4-(4-SUBSTITUTED BENZYLIDENE)-5-IMIDAZOLONES

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ARTICLE INFO

Article history

Received 25/01/2017

Available online
09/02/2017

Keywords

*Sulphoxy Benzoyl Glycine,
Oxazolones,
Zeolite Catalyst,
5-Imidazolones,
Antimicrobial Activity.*

ABSTRACT

Imidazolones are believed to be associated with several pharmacological activities. Their significance lies in the fact that they show diverse biological activities. Which include anticancer, anticonvulsant, antiparkinsonian, CNS depressant, antimicrobial, antihelminthic, anti HIV, anti-inflammatory etc. However no work is reported on imidazolone from substituted benzoyl glycine. Therefore it was thought interesting to attempt synthesis of imidazolones containing new substituent and study their antimicrobial activity. In the proposed work, we have reported eight newly synthesized sulphoxy substituted imidazolones from oxazolones and 4-chloroaniline in presence of zeolite as a catalyst. The oxazolones were obtained from 3-sulphoxy benzoyl glycine and variously substituted aromatic aldehydes in presence of anhydrous sodium acetate and acetic anhydride. The characterisation of these compounds was made by chemical properties, elemental analysis and spectral data like IR, ¹H-NMR. In order to know antimicrobial property these compounds were assayed for their antimicrobial activity against the test organisms E.coli, K.pneumoniae, S.aureus, S.epidermis. Out of eight samples tested, sample 2g and 2c each. The compound containing -OH group showed antimicrobial activity against maximum number of organisms followed by sample 2h containing -OCH₃ along with -OH group. Thus it may be concluded that -OH group present on benzylidene moiety irrespective of its position shows antimicrobial property.

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Please cite this article in press as **Rajendra .M .Kedar et al.** Synthesis and Antimicrobial Activity of 1-(4-Chlorophenyl)-2-(3-Sulphoxyphenyl)-4-(4-Substituted Benzylidene)-5-Imidazolones. *Indo American Journal of Pharmaceutical Research*.2017;7(01).

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INTRODUCTION

Imidazolones form an important class of heterocyclic compounds since they can be converted into amino acid [1-2], used in drugs[3], pigments and electrodes[4]. They have also shown diverse bioactivities including anticancer[5], anti HIV[6], antiparkinsonian[7-8], CNS depressant[9], antihelmintics[10]. Gabillet S, et al reported A Phosphine-Catalyzed Preparation of 4-Arylidene-5-imidazolones [11]. Snehalatha P and Subhashini N. J. P carried out, "Synthesis, characterization and biological evaluation of novel imidazolones derived from azlactones[12]. Ming and coworkers[13] synthesized 2-alkoxy 4H-imidazole-4-ones from azawitting reaction of iminophosphorane with phenyl isocyanate to form carbodiimide which on subsequent reaction with ROH in presence of RONA gave the target compounds. Kedar and Dehmukh[14] reported "synthesis of 1-(4-methyl phenyl)-2-(3-bromo phenyl) -4-(4-substituted benzylidene) -5-imidazolones. Chopra et al [15] carried out Microwave assisted synthesis of some 5-substituted imidazolone analogues as a new class of nonpurine xanthine oxidase inhibitors. However no work is reported on imidazolones synthesized from substituted benzoyl glycine. Thus, due to their diverse applications and also part of our study, it was thought interesting to synthesize some new imidazolones containing different substituents and to screen some of them for their antimicrobial activity.

MATERIALS AND METHOD

Aromatic aldehydes, benzoyl glycine, 4-chloroaniline, sodium acetate, acetic anhydride and zeolite are required chemicals purchased from sd fine chemicals. All the chemicals used were of AR grade. Melting points were measured in open capillary tube. The purity of the compounds were checked by TLC on silica gel in petroleum ether and ethyl acetate (80:20). The IR spectra were recorded on Agilent Technologies Cary 630 FTIR. ¹H-NMR spectra were recorded on Bruker AVANCE 400MHz spectrometer using TMS as internal standard. This work involved condensation of 3-sulphoxy benzoyl glycine with substituted aldehyde in acetic anhydride in presence of anhydrous sodium acetate to obtain variedly substituted oxazolones. Oxazolones were further reacted with 4-chloro aniline in presence of zeolite as a catalyst to obtain the target compounds 1-(4-chlorophenyl)-2-(3-sulphoxyphenyl)-4-(4-substituted benzylidene)-5-imidazolones. In order to know their antimicrobial activity, these compounds were then tested for antimicrobial activity against four test organisms, Klebsiella pneumoniae, Staphylococcus aureus, E.Coli and Staphylococcus epidermidis.

METHOD

Step-I: Synthesis of 2-(3-sulphoxyphenyl)-4-(4-methoxybenzylidene)-5-oxazolone.

To the solution of 3-sulphoxy benzoyl glycine 2.14gm(0.01mol) in acetic anhydride, added 1.36gms of anisaldehyde(0.01mol) and then 0.7gms anhydrous sodium acetate (0.01mol). The contents were dissolved in ethyl alcohol. The solution was refluxed under water condenser for 3-hours. It was poured to ice cold water when a yellowish solid was obtained. Washed it 2-3 times with ice cold water and recrystallised from ethanol.

Yield: 65%

Molecular formula C₁₇H₁₂NO₅

Melting point: 145⁰C

Molecular weight: 342

IR (KBr) in cm⁻¹: 3045 (Ar,C-Hstr); 2937 (Aliph,C-Hstr); 1787 (C=Ostr); 1651 (C=Nstr); 1596 (C=Cstr); 1311 (C-O bend); 1263 (C-N bend); 1028 (S-O Asymmetric str); 981 (S-O symmetric str).

¹H-NMR(δ) : 8.27(d,2H,Ar-H); 8.11(d,2H,Ar-H); 7.66-7.68(t,1H,Ph-CH); 7.58-7.61(t,2H,Ar-H); 7.60(d,2H,Ar-H); 3.87(s,3H,-OCH₃).

Elemental analysis for C₁₇H₁₂NO₅ (342)

Calculated	%C=59.64	%H=3.50	%N=4.09	%S=9.35
Found	%C=59.60	%H=3.48	%N=4.02	%S=9.30

Step-II :- Synthesis of 1-(4-chlorophenyl)-2-(3-sulphoxyphenyl)-4-(4-methoxybenzylidene)-5-imidazolone

To the ethanolic solution of oxazolone(3.42gm,0.01M) obtained in step-I, added 4-chloro aniline (1.27gm,0.01M) and zeolite (1gm) as a catalyst followed by 1ml of 2% aq NaOH solution. The reaction mixture was reflux under water condenser for two and half hours it was allowed to cool and poured to ice cold water obtained colourless solid on acidification with dil HCl. Washed it 2-3 times with cold water and recrystallised from ethanol.

Yield: 60%

Molecular formula C₂₃H₁₆N₂SClO₄

Melting point: 235⁰C

Molecular weight: 451

IR (KBr) : 3030cm⁻¹(Ar,C-Hstr); 2925cm⁻¹(Aliph,C-Hstr); 1710cm⁻¹(C=Ostr); 1639cm⁻¹(C=Nstr); 1599cm⁻¹(C=Cstr); 1305cm⁻¹(C-O bend); 1258cm⁻¹(C-N bend); 1035cm⁻¹(S-O Asymmetric str); 1020cm⁻¹(S-O symmetric str)

¹H-NMR(δ) : 8.04(d,2H,Ar-H); 7.74(d,2H,Ar-H); 7.56-7.61(m,3H,Ar-H); 7.48-7.52(t,1H,Ph-CH); 7.29(d,2H,Ar-H); 7.14(s,1H,Ar-H); 6.92(d,2H,Ar-H); 3.78(s,3H,OCH₃)

Elemental analysis for C₂₃H₁₆N₂SClO₄ (451.5)

Calculated	%C=61.12	%H=3.54	%N=6.20	%S=7.08	%Cl =7.86
Found	%C=61.05	%H=3.50	%N=6.18	%S=7.02	%Cl =7.78

REACTION

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The oxazolones required for the synthesis of imidazolones were prepared by condensation of newly synthesized 3-sulphoxy benzoyl glycine with variedly substituted aldehydes in presence of anhydrous sodium acetate in acetic anhydride. Their formation was confirmed by physical and chemical tests. Thus eight variedly substituted oxazolones were obtained from different aldehyde and 3-sulphoxy benzoyl glycine. The target compounds 1-(4-chlorophenyl)-2-(3-sulphoxyphenyl)-4-substituted arylidene)-5-Imidazolones were synthesized by reacting each of these oxazolones with p-chloroaniline in ethanolic medium in presence of zeolite as a catalyst. It offered easy to workout methodology and also reduced reflux time to two and half hours. The compound (2a) gave positive test (orange colour) with ethanolic solution of 2,4-dinitrophenyl hydrazine in presence of cone H_2SO_4 confirming the presence of (2a). It showed absorption bands at 2925cm^{-1} due to Aliphatic C-H str; 1710cm^{-1} due to C=O str; 1639cm^{-1} C=N str; $1035\text{-}1025\text{cm}^{-1}$ S-O Asymmetric str and symmetric str 690cm^{-1} C-Cl str similarly $^1\text{H-NMR}$ spectrum of 2 (a) showed the following chemical shift (δ) 8.04(d,2H,Ar-H); 7.74(s,1H,Ar-H); 7.56-7.61(m,3H,Ar-H); 7.48-7.52(t,1H,Ph-CH); 7.29(d,2H,Ar-H); 7.14(s,1H,Ar-H); 6.92(d,2H,Ar-H); 3.78(s,3H, O-CH_3) Which tallies with Molecular formula of target compound 2a $\text{C}_{23}\text{H}_{16}\text{N}_2\text{SClO}_4$. Elemental analysis also supported this formula experimental value of which are comparable with calculated ones all these evidences support the formation of 2(a) similarly other target compound (2b-2h) were synthesized by employing above mentioned procedure.

Table-1: List of synthesized compounds, their % yield and melting points.

Sr. No.	Compound	%Yield	Melting Point (in °C)
1	1-(4-chlorophenyl)-2-(3-sulphoxyphenyl)-4-(4-methoxy benzylidene)-5-Imidazolone.(2a)	60	235
2	1-(4-chlorophenyl)-2-(3-sulphoxyphenyl)-4-(4-nitrobenzylidene)-5-Imidazolone.(2b)	65	290
3	1-(4-chlorophenyl)-2-(3-sulphoxyphenyl)-4-(4-hydroxybenzylidene)-5-Imidazolone.(2c)	68	220
4	1-(4-chlorophenyl)-2-(3-sulphoxyphenyl)-4-(4-dimethylaminobenzylidene)-5-Imidazolone.(2d)	62	310
5	1-(4-chlorophenyl)-2-(3-sulphoxyphenyl)-4-(3,4,5tri methoxybenzylidene)-5-Imidazolone.(2e)	64	170
6	1-(4-chlorophenyl)-2-(3-sulphoxyphenyl)-4-(4-chlorobenzylidene)-5-Imidazolone.(2f)	69	230
7	1-(4-chlorophenyl)-2-(3-sulphoxyphenyl)-4-(2-hydroxy benzylidene)-5-Imidazolone.(2g)	69	210
8	1-(4-chlorophenyl)-2-(3-sulphoxyphenyl)-4-(4-hydroxy3-methoxybenzylidene)-5-Imidazolone.(2h)	70	160

ANTIMICROBIAL ACTIVITY

Method for the determination of antimicrobial activity

The newly synthesized eight compounds 2(a-h) were screened for their antimicrobial activity against *E.coli*(gram -ve), *K.pneumoniae*(gram -ve) ,*S. aureus* (gram +ve) and *S. epidermis*(gram +ve) by using agar disc diffusion method [16] at concentration of 100 µgm/ml in DMF as a solvent. Each standardized test organism (0.1ml)was spread on the solidified sterile agar plates.

Table 2 : Antimicrobial activity of imidazolones.

Sr. No	Sample	<i>E-Coli</i> Zone of inhibition in mm	<i>K. pneumonie</i> Zone of inhibition in mm	<i>S. aurous</i> Zone of inhibition in mm	<i>S. epidermis</i> Zone of inhibition in mm
1.	SACH (2a)	-	6	-	-
2.	SACH (2b)	6	-	-	-
3.	SACH (2c)	10	11	-	13
4.	SACH (2d)	7	-	-	-
5.	SACH (2e)	-	6	-	-
6.	SACH (2f)	-	-	-	-
7.	SACH (2g)	12	13	-	10
8.	SACH (2h)	13	11	-	-

After incubation period of 18 hours at 37⁰C, the trays were examined for bacterial growth .and zones of inhibition (in mm) were determined and are given in table 2. From these values, it follows that imidazolone containing -OH as substituent(2g and 2c) showed antimicrobial activity against maximum number of organisms followed by 2h ,each of which showed antimicrobial activity against three and two organisms respectively.However, 2a,2d, and 2e showed antimicrobial activity against one organism only.

CONCLUSION

Hence we could synthesize a new series of imidazolones by introducing sulphoxy group as one of the new substituents. Use of zeolite as a catalyst afforded us increase in percent yield and reduction in reflux time. From antimicrobial study it appeared that -OH group(irrespective of its position) as a substituent played a vital role in imparting antimicrobial property to imidazolones, particularly, the substituents like -OH , -OCH₃attached to benzylidene moiety enhanced the antimicrobial activity of the compounds. Therefore, it may be suggested that more series of compounds are needed to be synthesized by introducing new substituents on benzylidene moiety in order to enhance its value as a drug.

Table 3 : Photos showing Antimicrobial activity of imidazolones.

DECLARATION OF INTEREST

There is no conflict of interests

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

The authors are thankful to the authority of Shri Shivaji Science College Amravati for providing laboratory facilities and to SAIF Punjab University, Chandigarh for analytical data.

List of abbreviations

- A.R -Analytical Reagent
- Ac₂O - Acetic anhydride
- Et-OH - Ethanol
- TLC -Thin layer chromatography
- TMS -Tetra methyl silane
- Ar -Aromatic
- Cl-ph-NH₂ -4-chloro aniline

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